

Analyzing the Impact of Dogmatism on New Product Adoption

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Abstract

This empirical study explores impact of dogmatism on new product adoption in the Context of Pakistan. The Dogmatism is used as independent variable, new product adoption is used as dependent variable in this Research, and Mobile phone industry is selected for this study. Survey method is used to collect data; Results are supporting the Hypothesis that there is negative impact of dogmatism on new product adoption. This study is one among few Studies which have explored the impact of dogmatism on new product adoption. This study will help marketers understanding the importance of consumer personality trait dogmatism and its significant impact on the adoption behavior of the consumers in the cell phone products.

Keywords: Dogmatism, New product adoption

Introduction

In these days of modern technology and fast economic cycle it is important for the marketers to understand the personality traits which will effect on the buying the consumer products. Because we have to predict the behavior of the consumer that which type of the product they are going to purchase it. In this connection this research is focusing on the especial personality trait dogmatism and its effect on the new product adoption in the Cell phone market. The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of dogmatism on the new product adoption in Pakistan.

Williams (2011) has mentioned the Pakistan as the fifth largest cell phone market in the world. As Cell phone is the technological product and its life cycle is very short so buyers buy cell phone frequently as compare to other products.(Douglas & Craig, 2011) included Pakistan among the next Eleven best markets for the Multinational Corporations (MNCs) in the world after the BRICS (Brazil, Russia India, China, South Africa) Countries. Dogmatism means the rigidity to accept new ideas and new product adoption means accepting new ideas to purchase the new or innovative product.

Several studies are being conducted to investigate either there is positive or negative impact of dogmatism on the new product adoption, according (Blake, Perloff, & Heslin, 1970) close minded

people are interested in new products however (Mikol, 1960) suggested that there is negative relationship between Dogmatism and new product adoption. So the Purpose of this study is to examine that either there is positive or negative impact of Dogmatism on new Product adoption in the context of Pakistan. This study will help the managers of cell phone companies to understand the buying behavior of technological products and formulating the marketing strategies to capture the Customers in competitive market.

Literature review

Dogmatism is a characteristic of the personality concept of some individuals that their information, knowledge and experiences are absolutely right (Rokeach, 1954). Dogmatism is not old concept as we studied chemistry and physics and other subjects at the start of the first standard because these are centuries old concept means there is lot of research has been done on these subjects but dogmatism is new and latest concept. (Rokeach, 1954) was the first to introduce this concept. And he has also given the scale for measuring the degree of dogmatism whether people may be highly dogmatic or low dogmatic. This concept of dogmatism was purely based on the following categories patience; self-image and deliberately disliking the views of other people (Swink, 2011).

Merriam- Webster dictionary defines dogmatism as

1. *Positiveness in assertion of opinion especially when unwarranted or arrogant.*
2. *A view point or system of ideas based on the insufficient examined premises.*

(Rokeach, 1954) was studying in Michigan state university. He wrote first three articles on the concept of dogmatism. First was the establishment of the concept of dogmatism in 1954. Second was the notable difference of the concept as inflexibility in thoughts (Rokeach, McGOVNEY, & Denny, 1955). Third was introduction of measures from which the concept can be quantified by the use of scale items and these are linked with the personality of an individual and made a correlation in between them (Rokeach & Fruchter, 1956). Other psychologists also contributed in the concept of dogmatism by using the items of Rokeach scale and lot of modifications checked the reliability of the scale cut most of the items of the scale ((Rokeach & Fruchter, 1956), (Vacchiano, Strauss, & Hochman, 1969), (Troidahl & Powell, 1965).

But now the new, valid and reliable scale which can be used to measure degree of Dogmatism also different psychologists contributed in the development of the scale. (Altemeyer, 1996), (Altemeyer, 2002), (Crowson, DeBacker, & Davis, 2008)

Dogmatism refers to person's ability to modify the ideas or thoughts by its own ways according to will and wish of that individual. And it is also refers if a person is highly dogmatic on the scale than that individual is reluctant to accept new situation from the environment and individual will not change himself or herself in the new situation simply dislike the new situation but except only if that is guided by the opinion leader opinion expert which the individual aspires to be like that person. These leaders can be religious scholars or political figures (Rokeach, 1960).

the concept of Dogmatism was further refreshed by (Rokeach, 1960).

1. Dogmatism was called as thought process not just inflexibility in thoughts.
2. This was linked with the authority.

3. Dogmatic people don't have patience they are very much emotional people.
4. Dogmatic people always repel the information which is against their thoughts.
5. The view or thought of dogmatic people can be changed with the help of religious or political figure.

Another research was done which focused on two things.

1. To check the relationship between personality characteristics and new product adoption.
2. Highly dogmatic people can be changed to purchase new product only when the product is latest and recent. (Blake, et al., 1970).

Most of the researchers suggest that highly dogmatic people are not accepting the new products. Another research suggest that when measuring the level of dogmatism one are called as highly dogmatic and others are called as low dogmatic the characteristics of the highly dogmatic as compare to the low dogmatic people is that highly dogmatic people will not listen the new music as compare to low dogmatic people (Mikol, 1960). Another study says that there is inverse relationship between dogmatism and purchase of novel artistic work like paintings. (Frumkin, 1963). Another study research says that dogmatic people also changing their attitude or thought just because this was caused by the society as morally positive otherwise low dogmatic people are changing just because of abstract knowledge about the subject or matter (Jamias & Troidahl, 1968)

Other study suggested that dogmatic people are not in a position to learn new things or change the old or past concepts, but the degree of flexibility and inflexibility in thinking is only limited with the personality of a particular individual and each and every individual has its own personality (Ehrlich & Lee, 1969) individual can be dogmatic based on the opinion leader they choose some may change their ideas because of political personality or religious persons persuasion or even not dogmatic in other perspectives as well as. (Ehrlich & Lee, 1969) totally Milton Rokeach established the concept of dogmatism and provided the scale how to measure

it and describe it as inflexibility in thinking (Rokeach, 1954)

Other psychologists say that it is based on the individual differences and this concept is linked with the personality of individual as called as the particular trait (Vacchiano, et al., 1969) Some other psychologists say that a particular individual can be dogmatic on particular issue or subject but it cannot be dogmatic on another issue (Ehrlich & Lee, 1969)

Highly dogmatic people are not accepting new product as compare to low dogmatic people this is just because highly dogmatic are looking uncertainty and impatience in the new thing while this was totally opposite to the low dogmatic people but this also true that opinion leader with the help of persuasion can easily change the mind of the highly dog people so that he can purchase totally new product (Rokeach, 1960)

New Product Adoption

Another study which shows the relationship between dogmatism and innovation of product but by providing a gift. This shows that a person who is highly dogmatic and giving the gift to another person will be more innovative in terms of purchasing the product for his friend and as compare to low dogmatic people these people are less innovative when they are purchasing the new product. (Coney & Harmon, 1979)

It is difficult for the researcher to predict the behavior of the consumer on the basis of personality variables that which product the consumer purchase and what would be choice criteria for the consumer in selection of new product (Kassarjian, 1971) But the other researcher to some extent said that there are certain variables which can predict the behavior of consumer that which product and what choices the consumer made in a particular product category. This study was an aid to psychographic variables (Belk, 1975) The study of relationship between dogmatism and innovativeness by (Jacoby, 1971) and duplicated by (Coney & Harmon, 1979)

This shows that dogmatism and innovativeness are inversely proportional to each other if person buys product for himself but not for the other (Jacoby,

1971) New product adoption for the marketers the behavior of the consumer is very important in terms of the new product adoption. Because it will be helpful for the marketers to communicate with other consumers as well as just like word of mouth communication among consumers (Rogers Everett, 1995) Most of the research suggested that highly educated, young and high income consumers can easily adopt innovative product more quickly (Gatignon & Robertson, 1985) The inborn consumer creativeness and new product adoption were positively related in the software products but not in the food product category (Foxall, 1995) Some other factors like creative inclination in product and personality characteristics to motivate other or to get the work from the others and proactive behavior is also linked with new product adoption. (Gatignon & Robertson, 1989; Midgley & Dowling, 1978) (Rogers Everett, 1995) It is difficult to find relationship between innovativeness and product benefits.

Theoretical frame work

In this study Dogmatism is being used as independent variable and New Product Adoption is being used as dependent variable, according to (Mikol, 1960) the highly dogmatic people are not adopting the new product especially the musical instruments as compare to low dogmatic people. Means there is negative impact of dogmatism on new product adoption. According to the (Blake, et al., 1970) there is no negative impact of dogmatism on new product adoption. This study was done in the foreign not in the context of Pakistan. But in our research we are going to check the impact of personality trait dogmatism on new product adoption especially the cell phone brands are used to check the impact and for that we have selected the upper areas of Sindh province in Pakistan. The people who are living in the upper Sindh their demographic profile is totally different from the metropolitan cities of Pakistan. In this study we have used the updated version of the dogmatism scale and the updated and modified version of the new product adoption. We have used the regression statistical technique and selected dogmatism as independent variable and new product adoption the cell phones as dependent

variable. This research is in the context of Pakistan and cell phone market is the most profitable business to the multinational companies working in Pakistan.

Proposed Hypothesis

H: There is negative impact of Dogmatism on new product adoption.

Methodology

The questionnaire of the study is comprised of two parts first part includes measurement constructs of the variables used in the study and second part consist on Demographic variables, in the first part Dogmatism as independent variable is measured by adapted scale of (Altemeyer, 1996) and New product adoption as dependent variable measured by adapted scale of (Goldsmith, 2001)

Dogmatism scale is consist of 20 Items and New Product adoption scale is consist of six items,

The questionnaire was tested in panel experts and few questionnaires were distributed into the small number of respondents to assess the suitability of

Results

Demographic Profile Table No: 1

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	135	79.4
Female	35	20.6
Age		
15-20	56	32.9
21-25	67	39.4
26-30	28	16.5
31-35	9	5.3
36-40	5	2.9
41-45	5	2.9
Education		
INTERMEDIAT	14	8.2
GRADUATE	91	53.5
MASTER	52	30.6
MS&Phd	13	7.6
Monthly Family income		
20000 – 40000	89	5.4
40001 – 60000	46	27.1
60001 – 80000	14	8.2
80001 -100000	12	7.1
100001 – 300000	9	5.3

Scales before distributing randomly to whole sample, five point likert scales was used and respondents were suggested to select the value 1- Strongly Agree to value 5 Strongly Disagree

Data Collection

Data was collected from four Major Cities of Sindh Province like Larkana, Sukkur, Khairpur, Shikarpur and Dadu district, 200 Questionnaires were randomly distributed among different Business Schools of these Cities. Because the sample of this research was Students, because they use to buy new cell Phones Frequently. The questionnaires which were distributed directly by Researcher were in English language (which is not native language but used as Official Language in Pakistan).

Data Analysis

Data is cleaned and screened and analyzed through Statistical Package for Social sciences (SPSS Version 16) Software, regression analysis statistical technique is used to test the hypothesis, for the data analysis first of all data was screened and cleaned and then data was analyzed to test the hypothesis.

Profile of Participants

The respondents profiles Gender, Age Education and monthly family income are Shown in Table (1) there were total 170 respondents out of which 135 (79.4%) were Males and 35 (20.6%) were Females, Majority of the Respondents were Between Age of 21-years to 25-years (39.4%), according to Education most of the Respondents were Graduates (53.5%) as sample was students so majority of the Respondents were young that's why Students sample was selected they used to buy cell phone in Pakistan. Data is collected from Larkana, Sukkur, Shikarpur and Khairpur because these are the largest cities of North Sindh,

Reliability Table no 2

Variable	Cronbach's alpha
Dogmatism	.602
New Product Adoption	.644

In table no 2 the Reliability is checked to confirm that measurement Scale is Reliable and Consistent theCronbach's alpha value of Cronbach's alpha with range of more than 0.60 is considered acceptable and good. This is used as a guideline to test the Reliability of the variables. Values of Cronbach's alpha are Greater than .60 showing good reliability.

Regression Analysis

Table No : 3Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	3.216	1.532		2.099	.037	.191	6.241
	m_DOGT	.227	.036	.442	6.386	.000	.157	.298

a. Dependent Variable: m_NPA

Table No:4
R Square

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig
1	.442 ^a	.195	.191	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), m_DOGT

Table No:4
R Square

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Sig
1	.442 ^a	.195	.191	.000

b. Dependent Variable: m_NPA

Findings

Regression analysis is used to test hypothesis, results in the Table No 3 depict that dogmatism has significant impact on new product adoption (Standardized Beta = .442 and Sig (.037) and results of adjusted R square as shown in Table 4 describe that Dogmatism explains .19% Variance in the New Product Adoption

Conclusion

A theoretical Model was proposed to explore the impact of dogmatism and new product adoption in cellular brands and companies of Pakistan. Hypothesis Regarding negative impact of dogmatism supported this shows that Dogmatism affects new product adoption negatively. In this research indirect relationship of dogmatism on new product adoption is proved and results shows that Dogmatism as independent variable effects New product adoption.

This Research concludes that consumer personality characteristics or trait has an impact on when the consumer are buying the product. Dogmatism affects negatively on the new product adoption in cell phone suggest that there is high degree of dogmatism among the consumers of the upper Sindh and our sample was mostly youngsters which are also supporting the model. Previously it was said that only old age people are becoming more dogmatic and then they are not purchasing the new product but from this study it is proved that even youngsters if are highly dogmatic they are also not purchasing the new product. For the marketing companies it is suggested that they should use authoritative people when they are advertising the brand because of that these people will purchase the new cell brand of the company locally but now this is proved that even youngsters are also not purchasing the new product or innovative product due to dogmatism in the personality of the consumers. This support the hypothesis which we have made at the start.

For the marketers this research is help full when they are launching new brand of cell phone they should be careful about the personality of the youngsters that such kind of the celebrity should be used in the advertising campaign so that the followers of that celebrity will purchase the brand because of special reference power they have on the consumers. Also features plays very vital role in the cell phone brands. Because this will give competitive edge to the companies and they will easily grab the share from the market.

Limitations and Future Research

Due to selecting students as sample has narrowed research, so future Research is needed to overcome these limitations, Future Researchers can conduct research on other products as well as because this research is done on the cell phone products. It is also suggested other innovative products are also the areas for future research like iphone, tablets and laptops. Insurance companies are also the suggested study for the future.

Reference

Altemeyer, B. (1996). *The authoritarian specter*: Cambridge Univ Press.

- Altemeyer, B. (2002). Dogmatic behavior among students: Testing a new measure of dogmatism. *The Journal of social psychology, 142*(6), 713-721.
- Belk, R. W. (1975). Situational variables and consumer behavior. *Journal of Consumer research, 157-164*.
- Blake, B., Perloff, R., & Heslin, R. (1970). Dogmatism and acceptance of new products. *Journal of Marketing Research, 483-486*.
- Coney, K. A., & Harmon, R. R. (1979). Dogmatism and innovation: A situational perspective. *Advances in Consumer Research, 6*(1).
- Crowson, H. M., DeBacker, T. K., & Davis, K. A. (2008). The DOG Scale. *Journal of Individual Differences, 29*(1), 17-24.
- Douglas, S. P., & Craig, C. S. (2011). Convergence and divergence: developing a semiglobal marketing strategy. *Journal of International Marketing, 19*(1), 82-101.
- Ehrlich, H. J., & Lee, D. (1969). Dogmatism, learning, and resistance to change: A review and a new paradigm. *Psychological Bulletin, 71*(4), 249.
- Foxall, G. R. (1995). Cognitive styles of consumer initiators. *Technovation, 15*(5), 269-288.
- Frumkin, R. M. (1963). Sex, familiarity, and dogmatism as factors in painting preferences. *Perceptual and motor skills, 17*(1), 12-12.
- Gatignon, H., & Robertson, T. S. (1985). A propositional inventory for new diffusion research. *Journal of Consumer research, 849-867*.
- Gatignon, H., & Robertson, T. S. (1989). *Innovative decision processes*: Wharton School, University of Pennsylvania, Marketing Department.
- Goldsmith, R. E. (2001). Using the domain specific innovativeness scale to identify innovative internet consumers. *Internet Research, 11*(2), 149-158.
- Jacoby, J. (1971). Personality and innovation proneness. *Journal of Marketing Research, 244-247*.
- Jamias, J. F., & Troidahl, V. C. (1968). Dogmatism, tradition, and general innovativeness. *Milton Rokeach, Beliefs, Attitudes, and Values, San Francisco: Jossey-Bass*.
- Kassarjian, H. H. (1971). Personality and consumer behavior: A review. *Journal of Marketing Research, 409-418*.
- Midgley, D. F., & Dowling, G. R. (1978). Innovativeness: the concept and its measurement. *Journal of Consumer research, 229-242*.
- Mikol, B. (1960). The enjoyment of new musical systems. *The open and closed mind. New York: Basic Books, 270-284*.
- Rokeach, M. (1954). The nature and meaning of Dogmatism. *psychological review, 194-204*.
- Rogers Everett, M. (1995). Diffusion of innovations. *New York*.
- Rokeach, M. (1960). The open and closed mind.

- Rokeach, M., & Fruchter, B. (1956). A factorial study of dogmatism and related concepts. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 53(3), 356.
- Rokeach, M., McGOVNEY, W. C., & Denny, M. (1955). A distinction between dogmatic and rigid thinking. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 51(1), 87.
- Swink, N. (2011). Dogmatism and moral conviction in individuals: injustice for all.
- Troldahl, V. C., & Powell, F. A. (1965). A short-form dogmatism scale for use in field studies. *Social Forces*, 44(2), 211-214.
- Vacchiano, R. B., Strauss, P. S., & Hochman, L. (1969). The open and closed mind: A review of dogmatism. *Psychological Bulletin*, 71(4), 261.
- Williams, J. (2011). How many mobile phone users are there in Pakistan? *Online*(Cited 2011 October 7). Available from URL: <http://pepl.org.uk/2011/05/09/updated-how-many-moble-phone-users-are-there-in-pakistan>.